

IBM Deep Learning Notes

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Deep learning with tensorflow:

Data flow graphs: it consists of

- Nodes: Mathematical operations
- Edges: Multi-dimensional arrays (Tensors)

TensorFlow and Eager execution:

- Keras is the high level API for tensorflow but it does not work alone because it does not have an engine
- Eager execution is enabled by default for tensorflow low-level API
- Enabling eager tensors will enable accessing the intermediate results at anytime

Types of deep neural networks:

- Convolutional neural network (CNN)
- Recurrent neural networks (RNN)
- Restricted Boltzmann machine (RBM): used to find the patterns in data, in an unsupervised manner, they are shallow neural networks, used as building blocks to other networks in applications such as:
 - o Feature extraction
 - o Dimensionality reduction
 - o Pattern recognition
 - o Recommender systems
 - o Handling missing values
 - o Topic modelling
- Deep belief network (DBN): it is the old back propagation solution, and it is built by stacking multiple RBMs, some of its uses are:
 - o Image classification: it is a very accurate classifier, no need for big dataset
- Autoencoders: it is used for feature extraction and other tasks such as:
 - o Dimensionality reduction
 - o Image recognition

- Original goal of CNN: “how to create a good representations of the visual world in a way it could be used to support recognition”

Sequential models:

- A traditional neural model does not consider that the states are connected and have dependencies of sequential inputs, and for that need to use recurrent model.
- Recurrent networks keeps context
- One type of RNN is Elman and Jordan networks, also Hopfield networks are one type of RNNs. And recursive neural networks (RvNN)
- The LSTM has three gates:
 - o Write gate: writes data to the memory
 - o Read gate: reads data from the memory and sends it to the recurrent network
 - o The forget gate: maintains or deletes
- **Restricted Boltzmann Machine (RBM)**
 - o It's an unsupervised learning approach
 - o They are shallow neural networks that does not have a final classification layer but gives a features vector as an output
 - o There uses are:
 - Handling unlabeled data
 - Extract important features from the input
 - More efficient at dimensionality reduction then PCA
 - o They are one type of autoencoders but they are stochastic while the other autoencoders are deterministic
- **Autoencoders:**
 - o It's an unsupervised learning approach
 - o Autoencoders works by encoding the data to smaller set of features and decode them into the same input data again, and compare the difference from the original and this is the training process.
 - o Some uses:
 - Extract key image features
 - Improve training times
 - Improve the separability in comparison to PCA
 - o The autoencoder will get used after training by taking the central minimal set of features and considering them as representative to the object being clustered or classified

Deep learning fundamentals:

- A neural network is like any other type of network, it has interconnected nodes (biases) and the edges (weights) that joins them together.
- Neural networks receives an input apply complex calculations on and then use the output to solve a problem
- Classification is the process of categorizing a group of objects while only using a basic data features that describe them, some methods to do that are Logistic regression, SVMs, naive bayes and neural networks.
- The neural nets was born to increase the accuracy of a perceptron.
- Since its creation the name of a multi-layer perceptron stayed but the perceptron itself was replaced with a more powerful classifier.
- The network is needed for more complex patterns a single classifier cannot handle alone.
- The number of nodes required in a network grows exponentially with the number of possible patterns in the data.
- Choosing a deep net:
 - o Unlabeled data: feature extraction, unsupervised learning, pattern recognition
 - RBM
 - Autoencoder
 - o Labelled data:
 - RNTN and RNN for text processing
 - DBN and CNN for image recognition
 - RNTN and CNN for object recognition
 - RNN for speech recognition
- The vanishing gradient problem: as we can see the gradient are much smaller in the earlier layers that is why these layers train slowly, but here is the problem: the early layers are responsible to detect the simple patterns and building blocks, and that leads for training to take more time and less accurate results
- Overcoming the vanishing gradient:
 - o Using RBMs: since it can find patterns in the data by reconstructing the input. An RBM is called restricted because the neurons of the same layer have no connections between them.
 - RBMs takes the inputs and translate them into numbers and then retranslate the numbers into the same inputs with high accuracy.
 - Weights and biases has a very important role, since they allow the RBM to decipher the interrelationships among the input features, and decide which features are most important to detecting patterns
 - The steps of training a RBM are:

- Forward pass where each input get combined with a weight and the single bias passed to the hidden layer
- Backward pass where each activation is combined with an individual weight and the bias and the result is passed to the input layer
- The back propagation result get compared to the actual input using KL Divergence
- And this process get repeated until the input and the reconstructed result are as close as possible.
 - An RBM is from the family of autoencoders
- By combining the RBMs together and using a clever training method which results in DBMs, the vanishing gradient problem get solved,

Deep Belief networks:

- According to Geoff Hinton they are an alternative to backpropagation
- A deep belief network (DBN) is identical to MLP in structure but totally different in training.
- They constructed of many RBMs stacked together, where each hidden layer for one RBM is the visible layer for the one comes after it.
- The DBN intuition is that it is similar to a camera focusing a picture, i.e. processes the whole picture in every layer starting without features and adding the features in the deeper layers. In contrast a CNN detects smaller features in the beginning and combine them in the deeper ones.
- After training on unlabeled data, the network get trained on a small set of labelled data so that the features and the patterns get associated with a name, and this process changes the weights slightly and improves the accuracy of the model slightly
- It takes only a small labeled dataset
- The training does not take so much time and it is so accurate

CNNs:

- A convolutional network can have the following layers:
 - Convolutional
 - RELU
 - Pooling
 - Fully connected

- A disadvantage for them is the need for big labelled data for training

RNNs:

- The vanishing gradient problem exists with the RNN, and it get solved by using gates.
- Training a RNN for 100 time steps is equivalent to training a 100 layer feedforward neural network.

Autoencoders:

- It is useful when trying to understand the unlabeled data features, for the labeling process.
- Some types of AEs are:
 - o RBMs
 - o Denoising
 - o Contractive
- They are usually very shallow and does not have many layers, while deep AEs are useful for image dimensionality reduction.
- AEs are better than PCAs in dimensionality reduction, because it has an improved separation
- Mostly the same weights of the encoder get used in the decoder.

Recursive neural tensor networks RNTNs:

- They are binary trees where each leaf or root is formed of a group of neurons
- Better to use for a hierarchal structure of a set of a data than feedforward or recurrent networks.
- They get designed for sentiment analysis, language processing
- An RNTN consists of root and leaves
- The processing work starts from the leaves and goes up to the root
- Some of its applications is: image parsing
- There could be many tree structures that fits for processing the same sentence, and the score get produced in the root is how to find about which tree is best

Deep neural networks use cases:

- Machine vision
 - o Image classification
 - o Object recognition

- Clarifai is a platform to train deep learning models
- Video recognition
- Speech recognition
- Text processing
 - o Fact extraction
 - o Machine translation
 - o Sentiment analysis, MetaMind is a website for this application
 - o Character level text processing
- Some applications are:
 - o Cancer detection
 - o Drug discovery
 - o Radiology
 - o Finance
 - Portfolio application
 - Risk prevention
 - o Digital advertising
 - o Fraud detection
 - o Customer intel
 - o Plant illness and conditions

A deep net platform is a set of tools the engineers can build on top of optimizing the hyper parameters using an UI without the need to learn coding, it allows the user of:

- Choosing the type of model
- Data management/data wrangling
- Provides a UI
- infrastructure

its types

- Software platforms
- Full platforms

Software libraries: need to learn code to use them, it gives flexibility, which is a big advantage on platforms.

One platform was discussed is H2O.ai which offers

- multilayer perceptron models and a few other models such as GLM, distributed random forest, K-means clustering, naive bayes classifier, and
- back propagation is performed by means of L-BFGS algorithm

- besides a data munging capabilities. And support for other platforms such as HDFS, Amazon S3, SQL, No SQL,
- Modelling can be accessed using tools like python, R, JSON
- Visualize data using tableau, R-studio, and Microsoft excel
- Also offers ensemble training
- To build you own infrastructure the platform offers:
 - o in-memory map-reduce capability,
 - o distributed parallel processing,
 - o and columnar compression.

- Dato GraphLab create offers two deep nets and so many algorithms, for image data it will give a convolutional net, for any other type of data works with multi-layer perceptron. Besides graph analytics tools, It supports the following applications
 - o Text analytics
 - o Recommender
 - o Classification
 - o Regression
 - o Clustering

It provides support for the following databases:

- SQL
- Hadoop
- Spark
- Amazone S3
- Pandas
- HDFS

It has a UI and visualizations canvas

Types of storage GraphLab provides:

- SArray – columnar representation
- GPU support
- SFrame – tabular data structure
- SGraph – built in data structure

It also has an API

the libraries are pre-written code created by experts could be used to avoid reinventing the wheel or so to say. Some notable deep learning libraries are:

- DeepLearning4j
- Torch
- Caffe
- Theano: for education and scientific research.
- deepmat

Theano: it has extensions such as:

- Blocks platform: a wrapper for each Theano function allowing you to access the functions with parameters
- The Lasagne package allow you to built a net on top of theano by providing the net hyper parameters layer by layer
- Passage suited for text analysis applications that require recurrent net

and built by Yoshua Bengio and his team.

Caffe: was built mainly for computer vision, and it works with CPU and GPU as needed, and has interfaces for MatLab and Python, it is open source and supported by a large community, Caffe vectorizes the input data as Blobs

Tensorflow was slower then theano in 2016, TensorFlow supports Parallelism, Data parallelism allows you to train different subsets of the data on different nodes in a cluster for each training pass, followed by parameter averaging and replacement across the cluster.

Swig is an open source tool for connecting libraries across languages

Accelerating deep learning with GPUs:

- Deep learning is a computation resource consuming process which might take long time to be done in case insufficient resources get used in training the models.
- The main advantages of deep learning are:
 - Availability
 - Ease of use
 - Speed
 - Accuracy
- Deep learning pipeline:
 - Pre-processing data
 - Training the model

- Inference and deployment
- Using training acceleration enables training a better model and a bigger number of models, which could be used as an ensemble model.
- Acceleration hardware types:
 - Google TPU
 - Nvidia GPU
- The training operation is the most intensive and resource consuming process, since:
 - it consist of a forward pass and a backward pass
 - Iterative process, trial and error, optimization
 - It involves heavy computation
- Accelerating through parallelism which happens by running the processes such as matrix multiplication with GPUs instead of CPUs which run the processes sequentially.
- GPUs (Graphics processing units):
 - It has many cores to process data in parallel
 - Good at fetching large amounts of memory
 - Nvidia GPU:
 - Software: CUDA a high level programming language enable the user to write program for GPU processors
 - Cards: GTX, Tesla, the most important metric is the memory bandwidth.
 - AMD GPUs: uses OpenCL software which is not so popular
 - TPUs (TensorFlow Processing Units): developed specifically for TensorFlow
 - FPGAs (Field Programmable Gate Arrays): a programmable and customizable hardware for which you can build a circuit of resources, connect it to it, and exploit all the parallelism in the program, mainly built by intel.
- Limitations of GPUs:
 - Limited memory capacity
 - Not practical for very large datasets
 - Alternative: reading data from system memory (overhead)
 - Accessibility
 - Expensive, dependencies and incompatibilities
- Possible hardware choices:
 - A laptop with embedded GPU
 - Using a GPU on a cloud service, need to upload the dataset
 - Using a GPU cluster in the cloud, such as IBM cloud

- Using a GPU cluster on-premises
 - Keep your data locally
 - Cost-effective
 - Perfect for sensitive data
- IBM Power AI: the main issue that slows down the processing of deep learning models is the transfer of data through the PCIe, and for that Power Ai, takes advantage of NVLink to increase system bandwidth.
- NVLink: high bandwidth protocol that enables faster GPU-to-GPU communication, by providing multiple point-to-point connections. And it also connects between CPU and GPU
- In Power AI IBM uses Tesla 100, and Power8

- Most scientists usually use 4 or 8 GPUs when training a model on ImageNet-22K such as ResNet-101, since in this case training on a single GPU can take up to 16 days.
- Power AI Vision: automatic image and video analysis:
 - Classification
 - Object detection
 - Functions such as:
 - Data labeling
 - Pre-processing
 - Model training
 - Deployment
 - Inference
- A Deep learning Pipeline typically includes:
 - Creating the training task
 - Preparing the training data
 - Data pre-processing
 - Configuring the training hyper-parameters
 - Preparing the Deep Learning training framework
 - Selecting the Deep Neural Network Model (or DNN, for short)
 - Training the DNN Model
 - Packaging the new DNN Model ... and then deploying the API
 - And the ninth and final step is Testing the Model

Power AI vision usage:

- Upload and label the data
- Create deep learning model
 - o Select task
- Build model
- Train the model
- Deploy the model as an API
- test